

Assessment Of Parental Level Of Education In Relation To Academic Performance Of Their Children In Higher Institutions Of Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between students' socioeconomic background and academic performance of N C E students of Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto, Nigeria. The research design is correlational research design which is concerned with determining if relationship exists between two variables of parental educational background and students' academic performance. The population of the study consists of 25 lecturers as sample for this study using Krejcie & Morgan table for determining sample size. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample. The instruments used were questionnaire, in-depth interview schedule and documentary materials (students past exam scores in four selected subjects). Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Result of findings revealed that parental socioeconomic background significantly influenced students' academic performance; as students whose parents had better jobs and higher levels of educational attainment and who were exposed to more educational resources at home tend to perform better than their counterparts without such opportunities. The study recommended that government should improve the economic standard of the poor parents through proper poverty alleviation program.

Keywords: academic performance, students, parental educational background

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In educational institutions, success is measured by academic performance, or how well a student meets standards set out by educational administrators or the institution itself. The tracking of academic performance fulfils a number of purposes. Areas of achievement and failure in a student academic career need to be evaluated in order to foster improvement and make full use of the learning process. Results provide a framework for talking about how students fare in school, and a constant standard to which all students are held. Performance result also allows students to be ranked and sorted on a scale that is numerically obvious, minimizing complaints by holding teachers and schools accountable for the components of each and every grade.

Nigeria is a nation with people that are classified on the basis of socio-economic status. These classes are high, middle and low socio-economic status. This class or division has implication for the type of school a child goes to in Nigeria. School attendance influences school performance, which may be attributed to economic and social influence of the child's family background. The main source of conflict attitude in formal western

education in Nigeria today, is the cost of educational learning process at all levels. Children from high socio-economic background may stand a better chance of school attendance and good academic performance than children from low socio-economic background.

Socio-economic status is a broad construct representing a family's access to social and economic resources. Empirical investigations most frequently assess socio-economic status using measures of three key variables: family income, parents, educational level and parents' occupation (Bradley and Corwyn, 2002). Family income is an indicator of the financial resources available to a family, whereas parental education levels and occupation are indicators of the parent's intellectual resources and social status, or human and social capital (Conger and Donellan 2001). Other measures of socio-economic status include household composition, income to poverty ratio, and home ownership status (Hauser, 1994). A recent meta-analysis of studies examining the relationship of socio-economic status to academic outcomes showed that various components of SES (e.g, family income, parental educational level, parental occupation) have different effects on academic performance (Sirin, 2005).

Several factors have been advanced by researchers for the poor academic performance of students, among these factors parental socio-economic status exercise a greater impact. Parents' ability to provide the basic needs of their children in school such as registration fees, textbooks, writing materials, and other assistance are assumed to give students whose parents are from high socio-economic status an advantage over their counterparts from low socio-economic status. Despite the government plans to provide equal educational opportunity for all students, yet, socio-economic status is still assumed to be influential in enhancing the student's academic performance, hence, the need to study the relationship between parental level of education and see whether it has a direct influence on academic performance of students of Shehu Shagari college of Education, Sokoto. The specific objectives is therefore to find out the relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of NCE Students.

2.0 Review of Related Empirical Studies

Several research studies have been conducted throughout the world to examine the relationship between socio-economic background and student's academic performance. Researches indicated that children from low socio-economic status households and communities develop academic skills more slowly compared to children from high socio-economic status groups. Notably, researches have been conducted in both developed countries and developing countries.

In United State of America (USA) student Achievement in public schools has become a top priority for the United States government. With the passing of legislation in 1998 known as "no child left behind" (NCLB), Public schools have been mandated to have all students receive proficient scores on state assessment by the year 2014. This legislation has created much discussion and debated on the outcome factor of students' achievement. One of the most debated issues among educational professionals is the correlation between academic performance and socio-economic status of students.

Davies-Kean (2005), conducted research on "the influence of parent education and family income on child achievement: the indirect role of parental expectation and the home environment" using data from a national cross-sectional study, and concluded that parents' education has both direct and indirect relation to children's academic achievement.

The effects of the family and its socio-economic status on the performance of children in schools are inseparable. Parents with a high socio-economic status may likely influence their children to aim for more excellent achievement and good performance in school, when compared with those children with parents of low-socio-economic status. It is also found that parents being well educated may be better able to monitor, supervise and if necessary, personally assist the progress of their offspring in the school, for good academic performance, they may be able to hire tutors to improve their students' results.

Researches conducted in Britain found that socio-economics status had great influence on the academic performance of students. Entwistle and Wilson, (1977) observed that in Britain, some students obtain good results in school because of the good socio-economic standard of their family background. According to Springhal (1981), parents provide home for the head start of children and the material for learning. When a child is deprived of the essentials needs, he may be found to perform poorly in schoolwork. It is related in this

study, that most parent's income was found not to be sufficient to sustain academic and personal social life of the students in schools. This to a large extent affects the psychological or homeostatic balance in the class room which causes low concentration, low perception, frustration, sickness of emotional disability in academic performance of students in Britain (Springhal,1981).

Lareau (1987) in her studies on first grade classroom in a working-class community and middle-class community found that parents in the middle-class community tend to help their children more due to their better skills, the occupation status, income and time, compared to working class parents. In a related study Reay (2004) in one of her studies found that mothers from the middle class have a good educational background that enables them to inculcate academic values in their children, thereby promoting self-confidence and participation and transforming the child into a more positive attitude and behaviour of learning towards academic success.

In a recent study, it was found out that the educational background of the families in Britain plays an important role in academic success of the students, similarly; financial income of the student is also an important factor in the quality of education and the overall academic success among the students of different socio-economic status. It was also found that, when groups of students with similar background are compared, the students from a high socio-economic status outperform those from low socio-economic status on academic performance. High socio-economic status is related to better social support, fewer discipline problems and high social expectation. In another study Zorman (1969) showed that children whose parents have higher educational and professional qualifications are more successful in school than children whose parents have little or no educational and professional qualification. According to Johnson (1996), poverty of parents has elastic effects on their children academic works as they lack enough resources to sponsor their education in addition to good school, good housing facilities medical care and social welfare services.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODS

This study will use of the correlational survey design. Correlational research design attempts to determine if a relationship exists between two variables and the degree of the relationship. Correlational research is interested in attempting to determine whether there is a relationship or not between two or more quantifiable variables and to what degree the relationship exists but it does not indicate causation.

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of this study for interview comprises of twenty-five (25) lectures selected systematically based on department among those teaching only NCE 2 students (2023/2024 academic session) at Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto. The basis for this selection is the lectures are expected to be very familiar with the performance of their students of NCE 2 students. The college has seven schools: Education, Arts and Social Science, Languages, Sciences, vocational and technical education, Special and Adult and non-formal education, which comprise of twenty-nine (29) Departments.

3.2 Research Instruments

The research instruments to be used in conducting this study is parental socio-economic status questionnaire. The researcher adapted the Adoke's (1987) parental socio-economic status questionnaire to serve the objective of this study. The questionnaire is specifically designed to be responded by the NCE II students who form the population for this study. The instrument is going to be divided into two sections, section A' and B. Section A collects information about the respondent, while Section B contains a number of questions designed to measure facts about parental status, parental income, occupation, level of education and dwelling environment.

3.3 Method of Data Collection

The information to be use for this study will be obtained through both primary and secondary data. Data on parental socioeconomic status (primary data) will be obtained through the administration of questionnaire. The researcher also may interview some lecturers that were believed to have knowledge of the subject of this research.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

This study will adopt use of both the quantitative and qualitative methods of data analysis. The data to be obtained from administered questionnaire as well as mean scores of students' performance will be analysed

using descriptive statistics. Pearson “r” statistical method will be choosing to establish relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The information gathered from transcribed field notes, recordings from (IDTS) and documentary sources were analyzed and relevant information were retrieved and summarize.

4.1 Parental level of education and academic performance of N C E students

All the lecturers interviewed agreed that parental level of education influenced the academic performance of their children. Bakken (2003) averred that parental educational level correlated with children’s academic performance. All the lecturers interviewed agreed that there is a strong relationship. One of the lecturers interviewed stated that:

Parental educational level affects a student academic performance because of parents’ involvement in the education of their children. Students, who came from educated parents or guardians, are assisted by their parents and the parents provide all the academic needs of their children because these parents know the value and importance of education.

Another lecturer opined that:

Parental educational level positively affects students’ academic performance. This is because children always want to emulate their parents, thus a son of a professor will always strive towards attaining that level while a child whose father has only a secondary school certificate will be contented with the same. Children see their parents as role model and so copy from them.

All of the lecturers 100% interviewed agreed that parental level of education influenced student academic performance. This made the researcher to conclude that there is significant relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of students.

Table 1: Analysis of Lecturers’ Responses on the Relationship Between Parental Level of Education and Academic Performance Students.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	22	88%
Agreed	03	12%
Disagree	00	00%
Strongly Disagreed	00	00%
	25	100%

Source: fieldwork, 2024

4.2 Null Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁ *There is no significant relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of NCE students.*

The hypothesis was tested by subjecting the students’ scores of parental level of education and their academic performance scores to Pearson’s correlation analysis as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) on the Relationship between Students’ Academic Performance and Parental Level of Education.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Academic Perf.	250	96.16	18.14	.270	.000	H ₀ Rejected
Parental Level of Educ.	250	12.32	2.30			

From the result on table 4 above, students’ academic performance and their parental level of education were positively related and significant, Pearson’s $r(248) = .270, p = .000$. This indicates a significant relationship

between students' academic performance and their parental level of education because the p-value is less than the re-cal level of significance. Therefore, H_{01} which states that there is no significant relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of NCE students was rejected.

4.3 Findings

It was found that the majority of students whose parents are well educated perform better than students whose parents are less educated or illiterates. This indicates that in most cases the higher the level of education of parents the higher the academic performance of their children.

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4.4 Discussion Of Findings

Many studies have been conducted in respect of identifying the relationship between socioeconomic status of parents and the academic performance of students. This study also was an effort towards correlating some variables that do affects the academic performance of students especially those in National Certificate of Education (NCE) programme of Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto, Sokoto State.

The first hypothesis which proposed no significant relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of NCE students was rejected by the finding of the study. The finding showed that there is a significant relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of NCE students. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson's Correlation Analysis and the result indicates that students' academic performance and their parental level of education were positively related and significant, Pearson's $r(248) = .270, p = .000$. This indicates a significant relationship between students' academic performance and their parental level of education because the p-value is less than the .05 level of significance. The result reveals that parents' education has significant influence on the academic achievement of students. This is because parents' education has highest effect or predicts students' academic achievement the most. This observation provides the evidence that children of educated parents might performed better than children of uneducated parents.

The finding supports the results of Musgrave (2000) who reported that parents' level of education was the most important factor affecting students' academic achievement. Similarly, studies by Lockheed & Nyirongo (1984) and Trusty (2000) revealed significant relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of students. Since the studies were conducted in different parts of the world and Nigeria inclusive, one could say that parental level of education is predictive of students' academic performance. Here this study contributed to knowledge as being done by the previous studies conducted in different parts of the world. Davies-Kean (2005) conducted research using data from a national cross-sectional study, on "the influence of parental education and family income on child's achievement: the indirect role of parental expectation and the home environment" and concluded that parents' education has both direct and indirect relation to children's academic achievement.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research study seeks to examine the relationship between students' socioeconomic background and academic performance of NCE students of Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto. The study set to understand if there is any relationship between parental level of education and academic performance of students? From the analysis of data and discussion of findings, it could be concluded that, Parental level of education influences the academic performance of students.

Based on this finding the researchers recommended that, governments should organize programme that will truly help to solve the problem of poverty in the country. Existing social and economic policies should be improved to enable children from parents of low socioeconomic status to have equal opportunity of advancing the cause of their education. A special attention should be given to those who came from the family that have poor Parental educational background, this may be through free incentive lesson after classes or provision of extra moral classes as basic requirement for admission into higher institutions.

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